

DEVELOPMENT OF A VERSATILE RECYCLED COMPRESSION MOULDING COMPOUND MADE FROM UNCURED AEROSPACE PREPREG OFFCUTS

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ABSTRACT

Aerospace composites manufacturers discard anywhere from 30-50% of their prepreg fabric during the ply-cutting phase of manufacturing. This waste is mainly attributed to nesting pattern inefficiencies caused by limited production schedules, fixed prepreg roll widths, and limited material out-life. By recovering uncured prepreg offcuts from the ply cutter and transforming them into a recycled prepreg moulding compound (rPMC), it may be possible to produce complex semi-structural components with applications in the aerospace, automotive, or recreational sporting industries. This approach, however, carries with it two major manufacturing challenges. The first is related to order-of-magnitude differences in autoclave and compression moulding resin system processing viscosities. Autoclave resins are tailored to exhibit high levels of percolation to ensure proper fibre bed impregnation, whereas compression moulding compounds are designed to deform in shear, so that transport of fibre and resin occurs simultaneously, resulting in complete mould cavity filling. Secondly, compression moulding compounds are cured in as few as 3-5 minutes to satisfy the production rates of a given industry, whereas autoclave curing of large aerospace components can frequently take as long as 8-12 hours. This paper introduces a recycling framework for compression moulding of uncured prepreg offcuts. The processing aspect of the framework is discussed in detail, where thermochemical resin characterization and 1-D flow-compaction trials are used to understand the impact that a resin's processing viscosity has on the nature and magnitude of prepreg flow. A recycling process map is then presented in which flow tailoring and cycle time customization is achieved by increasing the resin's initial degree-of-cure through staging.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The makeup of a given composite waste stream depends on the type of parts being manufactured, the precursors and manufacturing processes used, and a host of other factors. Figure 1 shows an idealized waste stream for autoclave-cured aerospace parts, where waste sources are often divided into two categories: Manufacturing waste, which includes rejected or expired prepreg rolls, uncured ply-cutter offcuts, cured trimmings, and parts which are rejected due to failed quality inspection. And end-of-life waste, which includes all the material associated with components leaving service.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the aerospace composites waste stream (images courtesy of [1]).

Most of the composites recycling work found in the literature focuses on fibre reclamation of cured end-of-life waste through pyrolysis, mechanical comminution, or chemical solvolysis [2-5]. However, when applied to uncured manufacturing waste, these approaches downplay the value of the original resin by relegating it to low value chemical feedstock, or filler. With large increases in composite end-of-life waste projected to manifest by ~2040 [6], the amount of pristine prepreg being scrapped during the ply cutting phase of manufacturing is a more pressing matter. This waste represents a significant financial loss for original equipment manufacturers, as well as a negative impact on the environment due to current landfilling practices.

1.2 Manufacturing Challenges

Using recovered prepregs to compression mould highly featured parts is an interesting alternative to recycling via fibre reclamation, as it makes use of both fibre and original matrix. It is a process which has been studied at length for virgin prepregs with both thermoplastic [7-9] and thermoset [10, 11] matrices. Unidirectional tapes are used in all of these studies because they offer a balance between formability and mechanical performance. In the context of recycling, prepreg fabrics must be considered a priority over tapes, as they represent the majority of the waste generated [12]. Two processing challenges come with compression moulding prepreg strands with woven reinforcements. Woven architectures made up of inextensible fibres bundles in both warp and weft directions are prone to fibre locking which hinders bulk material flow through shear. Relatively low resin viscosities, a hallmark of autoclave prepregs, favour resin bleeding over shear flow which may lead to excessive resin loss and high void contents. These challenges are showcased in Figure 2 below where a rib-stiffened t-bracket was moulded using strands made from as-received autoclave prepreg.

Figure 2: t-bracket compression moulded using unmodified as-received prepreg offcuts.

For compression moulding to be economically competitive, cure times should generally be kept below 5 minutes. This presents yet another challenge to using recovered prepregs, as autoclave resin systems require cure times on the order of hours to attain sufficiently high degree-of-cures.

1.3 Scope

The objective of this paper is to introduce a recycling framework for compression moulding of uncured prepreg offcuts. The processing aspect of the framework is discussed in detail, where thermochemical resin characterization and 1-D flow-compaction trials are used to understand the impact that a resin's processing viscosity has on the nature and magnitude of prepreg flow for a commercially available autoclave material. A recycling process map is then presented in which flow tailoring and cycle time customization is achieved by increasing the resin's initial degree-of-cure through staging.

2 RECYCLING FRAMEWORK

The recycling framework proposed here consists of 6 steps: (1) Uncured prepreg waste recovery, (2) waste inspection, (3) material characterization, (4) staging, (5) prepreg stranding, and (6) the final recycled prepreg moulding compound (rPMC). Each of these steps and their impact on the material value is shown schematically in Figure 3 and discussed in detail below.

Figure 3: Visual representation of the recycling framework for transforming uncured prepreg offcuts into a recycled compression moulding compound.

- (1) Even though prepreg conditions are tightly controlled during production, ply-cutter offcuts are expected to be recovered with a range of out-times sometimes exceeding the manufacturer-specified out-life. Contamination in the form of debris or foreign resin/fibre is also expected. Finally, offcut size and shape will vary depending on the nesting patterns used.
- (2) A waste inspection step provides the user with valuable information about the resin type and/or as-received degree-of-cure of the recovered material. Inspection may include, but is not limited to, calorimetry, spectroscopy, and rheometry.
- (3) Resin thermochemical behaviour is studied and models for cure, viscosity, and glass transition temperature are populated. 1-D flow-compaction tests are also performed so that the relationship between processing parameters like resin viscosity and prepreg shear flow can be determined.
- (4) Using the resin behaviour models and flow-compaction testing results from the previous step, prepreg offcuts are staged to a specific degree-of-cure. This will enable fibre and resin to flow as needed through shear, while simultaneously reducing the cure time.
- (5) After staging, the prepreg is cut and slit into strands. Strand size is chosen to suit the application. For example, larger strands have been shown to result in better mechanical performance, while smaller strands exhibit better flow properties.
- (6) As a result of staging, the final rPMC features tailored flow and reduced cure time, but also extended room-temperature out-life and zero tack.

As mentioned in the last section, this paper presents a thermochemical resin characterization and 1-D flow-compaction testing of a recovered aerospace prepreg. Flow tailoring via staging is also discussed, which narrows the focus of this paper to Steps 3 and 4 of the framework.

3 MATERIALS

Two types of uncured prepreg waste were studied: plain weave (PW) and eight-harness satin (8HS) offcuts were obtained from production ply-cutters of Bell Helicopter Textron Canada and Bombardier Aerospace respectively. Both materials are impregnated with Cytec's Cycom[®] 5276-1 toughened epoxy; a system designed for primary aircraft structures with a specified service temperature range of -59 °C to 121 °C and high damage tolerance [13]. All offcut batches recovered were within the manufacturer-specified out-life; however, the exact out-time was not known.

4 RESIN CHARACTERIZATION

Using prepregs to study resin cure kinetics by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) is not recommended, as they often feature highly non-uniform resin morphologies which promote unpredictable variations in measured cure evolution magnitude. Furthermore, prepregs cannot be used to measure resin viscosity by parallel plate rheometry, as the presence of fibre increases the apparent viscosity by several orders of magnitude. For these reasons, and because it was not possible to procure resin film for this work, a resin extraction technique was developed based on the work of Siddiqui, et al. [14] and used to obtain enough neat resin (NR) to complete all necessary resin characterization.

4.1 Cure Kinetics

The curing behaviour of extracted 5276-1 resin was studied using a combination of conventional and modulated DSC. Dynamic (2 °C/min) and isothermal (120, 140, 160, 180 °C) scans were carried out on a Q100 DSC from TA Instruments to track the evolution of the resin cure rate under different time-temperature conditions. Three to five repetitions were performed for each testing condition.

Physics-based phenomenological cure modelling often provides a simple and effective way of approximating the behaviour of complex proprietary polymer systems for which a mechanistic approach would not be feasible. The method of isoconversional visualization described by Dykeman [15] showed that a two-reaction autocatalytic model including a diffusion factor (Equation 1) would adequately described the curing of 5276-1.

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K_1\alpha^{m_1}(1-\alpha)^{n_1} + \frac{K_2\alpha^{m_2}(1-\alpha)^{n_2}}{1 + \exp(D(\alpha - (\alpha_{C0} + \alpha_{CT}T)))} \quad (1)$$

In Equation 1, α is the degree-of-cure, K_1 and K_2 are Arrhenius coefficients given by Equation 2, n_1 , n_2 , m_1 , and m_2 are reaction orders, D is the diffusion factor, α_{C0} is the critical degree-of-cure at absolute zero, α_{CT} is the rate of increase of critical degree-of-cure with temperature, and T is temperature in units of Kelvin.

$$K_i = A_i \exp\left(\frac{-E_{a,i}}{RT}\right) \quad (2)$$

In Equation 2, A_i is the pre-exponential factor, $E_{a,i}$ is the activation energy, R is the universal gas constant, and T is, once again, temperature in units of Kelvin.

A weighted non-linear least-squares regression was used to obtain the ideal model parameters (shown in Table 1) and the experimental cure rate curves are plotted against the model predictions for both isothermal and dynamic test conditions in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Measured and predicted cure rate curves for extracted 5276-1 resin.

Table 1: Summary of cure kinetic parameters for 5276-1.

Parameter	Reaction 1	Reaction 2
A_i (s ⁻¹)	3.50×10^4	2.50×10^4
E_{Ai} (J/mol)	6.14×10^4	7.20×10^4
m_i	0.50	0.20
n_i	2.00	0.50
D	-	40
α_{C0}	-	-7.03×10^{-1}
α_{CT} (K ⁻¹)	-	3.73×10^{-3}

4.2 Rheology

The rheology of 5276-1 resin was studied by parallel plate rheometry using an AR2000 rheometer from TA Instruments. Dynamic (0.5, 1, 2 °C/min) and isothermal (80, 100, 120, 140, 160 °C) scans were performed at 1 Hz and 1.0 % strain to track the evolution of resin viscosity with respect to different time-temperature conditions. One to four repetitions were performed for each testing condition.

A modified version of the viscosity model proposed by Khoun et al. [16] was fit to the viscosity data obtained from **Error! Reference source not found.** and is shown in Equation 3:

$$\eta = \eta_1 + \eta_2 \left(\frac{\alpha_{gel}}{\alpha_{gel} - \alpha} \right)^{A+B\alpha+C\alpha^2}, \quad (3)$$

where η is the dynamic resin viscosity, η_1 and η_2 are Arrhenius terms given by Equation 4, α is the degree-of-cure, α_{gel} is the degree-of-cure at gelation, and A , B , and C are fitting parameters.

$$\eta_i = A_{\eta_i} \exp\left(\frac{E_{\eta_i}}{RT}\right) \quad (4)$$

In Equation 4, A_{η_i} is the Arrhenius pre-exponential factor, E_{η_i} is the amount of energy required to overcome the polymer's internal resistance to strain, R is the ideal gas constant, and T is the temperature in units of Kelvin.

A weighted non-linear least-squares regression was again used to obtain the ideal model parameters (shown in Table 2) and the experimental viscosity evolution curves are plotted against the model predictions for both isothermal and dynamic test conditions in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Measured and predicted isothermal viscosity curves for extracted 5276-1 resin.

Table 2: Summary of viscosity model parameters for 5276-1.

Parameter	Term 1	Term 2 (Gel Effects)
A_{η_i}	1.00×10^{-13}	9.37×10^{-3}
E_{η_i}	1.01×10^5	2.11×10^4
α_{gel}	-	0.63
A	-	4.06
B	-	$-0.23 T + 96.6$
C	-	$0.31 T - 136.4$

4.3 Glass Transition

The relationship between degree-of-cure and glass transition temperature for 5276-1 was explored by modulated DSC. Specimens of extracted NR and of both 8HS and PW prepregs were processed under a series of different time-temperature conditions to obtain incremental levels of cure from 0-1. A summary of the tests performed is shown below in Table 3.

Table 3: DSC test matrix for 5276-1 glass transition temperature characterization.

Test Type	Form	Test Conditions
Dynamic Ramp	NR	2 °C/min
	8HS	
Isothermal Dwell	NR	80, 100, 120, 140, 160 °C
Sequential Ramps	PW	150, 155, 160, 175, 275 °C
Interrupted Isotherms	NR	5 – 60 min; $\Delta t = 5$ min
	8HS	32, 87, 107, 122, 130.5 min

The DiBenedetto relationship [17], shown in Equation (5), was chosen to represent the glass transition temperature versus degree-of-cure behaviour of 5276-1.

$$\frac{T_g - T_{g0}}{T_{g\infty} - T_{g0}} = \frac{\lambda \alpha}{1 - (1 - \lambda)\alpha} \quad (5)$$

In Equation 5, T_{g0} , $T_{g\infty}$, and T_g are the initial ($\alpha = 0$), final ($\alpha = 1$), and intermediate ($0 < \alpha < 1$) glass transition temperatures respectively. λ is a fitting parameter which varies between 0 and 1.

Figure 6: Measured and predicted glass transition temperatures of 5276-1 at various degrees-of-cure.

5 FLOW-COMPACTION TESTING

5.1 Apparatus

A flow-compaction testing apparatus (Figure 7) consisting of a 12.7 mm wide rectangular piston-channel mould was designed, based on the work of Hubert [18], to simulate various processing conditions that occur during compression moulding. The apparatus consists of the following features:

- A gap tolerance of 0.0127 mm between the piston and channel walls to prevent resin or fibre from flowing in the z-direction during testing.
- A removable flange with press fit alignment pins facilitates cured specimen removable.
- Firerod resistive cartridges heaters, an SD PID limit controller, and a K-type thermocouple from Watlow are integrated in to upper and lower copper plates to promote controlled heating across the mould surfaces.
- An HS25 LVDT from Vishay Precision Group is used to obtain precise displacement data for the upper and lower tooling surface gap.

Finally, the flow-compaction apparatus was mounted on an Insight 5 kN table-top electromechanical testing frame from the MTS Corporation. This provides the user with the ability to precisely control displacement rates, while measuring force with the frame's 5 kN load cell.

Figure 7: Instrumented flow-compaction apparatus.

5.2 Specimen Preparation

Prepreg strands were stored in sealed bags at $-18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until needed for testing to preserve the state of the resin and avoid moisture contamination. Shortly before testing, the strands were thawed at room temperature until the still-sealed bag is free of condensation and no longer cool to the touch. 12.7 mm x 12.7 mm strands are then stacked in a $[0_6]_T$ configuration and the uncompressed specimen thickness (h_0) and initial mass (m_0) were measured prior to testing.

5.3 Testing Procedure

A prepared specimen is placed inside the channel mould which in this case was preheated to the $140\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The piston head is initially lowered at 0.5 mm/s until a small preload of 25 N is applied to the specimen at which point the crosshead position is held constant for one-minute to ensure that each test is performed under uniform isothermal conditions. The specimen is then subjected to constant-displacement loading until a force of 1000 N is reached, at which point the frame switches to PID

force-control for the remainder of the test. A nominal mould closure rate of 0.1 mm/s was chosen based on the work of Rasheed [19] who showed that charges of 5HS/PPS flakes loaded at excessively slow rates (0.005 mm/s) could experience local fibre jamming resulting in resin starved regions and hindered overall material flow.

5.3 Strain Measurement

Unlike Hubert [18] who measured final specimen length (L_f) using a caliper, the method used here utilizes optical micrographs of the specimen's midplane to obtain a more accurate measurement. This approach was shown to be necessary when dealing with woven prepreg, as they feature a transition zone near the edge-of-part [20]. L_f is determined using a minimum fibre volume content limit of 20%, as shown in Figure 8. This cut-off reflects fibre volume contents typical of SMC (20-30%) and BMC (10-20%) compression moulded parts as per B. T. Astrom [21]. Thus, anything below 20% is considered resin bleed. In many of the specimens tested, a dip below 20% was observed immediately after the edge of the original prepreg stack. This often also coincided with the end of a large concentration of 0° fibres, but, in almost all cases, the fibre volume content quickly increases to well over 20% for the remainder of the specimen length. For this reason, only the final dip below the 20% is used to determine the end-of-part.

Figure 8: Illustration of the method used to determine final specimen shear strain.

As in Hubert [18], the final shear strain (e_x^S), is calculated using the Green tensor evaluated in the x-direction, which is shown in Equation 6:

$$e_x^S = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(1 + \frac{L_f - L_{0,avg}}{L_{0,avg}} \right)^2 - 1 \right], \quad (6)$$

where, $L_{0,avg}$ is the average specimen length measured during specimen preparation.

The Green strain tensor includes quadratic terms in addition to the small strain terms more commonly known as engineering strain. This makes the Green strain tensor rotation independent and preferred for large deformations.

5.1 Effect of Resin Viscosity

For a constant temperature, a thermoset's processing viscosity can be increased by increasing its initial degree-of-cure. The 5276-1 cure kinetic and viscosity models developed in Section 4.1 and 4.2 were used to determine the range of initial degrees-of-cure that correspond to viscosities similar to conventional compression moulding materials like PEEK, PEKK, and PPS for a cure temperature of 140 °C. Several points were selected from this range for testing and are shown Table 4.

Table 4: Staging conditions for flow-compaction testing.

Code	Staging Conditions	T_g	Staged Degree-of-Cure	Viscosity
S1	32 min at 120 °C	7.15 °C	0.11	11 Pa-s
S2	87 min at 120 °C	26.2 °C	0.24	43 Pa-s
S3	107 min at 120 °C	32.4 °C	0.29	71 Pa-s
S4	122 min at 120 °C	41.3 °C	0.35	142 Pa-s
S5	130.5 min at 120 °C	45.8 °C	0.38	205 Pa-s

The shear strains obtained by applying Equation 6 to the micrographs of all the staged specimens tested are plotted against their corresponding resin viscosities in Figure 9. The error bars used represent the minimums and maximums instead of standard deviations. Specimen micrographs

representative of each condition's average value are also included in

Figure 10 to illustrate the changes in specimen morphology observed.

Figure 9: Shear strain versus resin viscosity for all staging conditions tested.

Figure 10: Representative specimen micrographs for each staged condition tested.

For $\eta = 11$ Pa-s (S1), very little shear strain is observed in the specimens tested ($e_x^S = 0.48$). In fact, micrographs show that resin percolation leaves the original fibre stack almost entirely undisturbed except for a few 90° tows at the very edge of the specimen which are drawn out by the flow. From $11 \text{ Pa-s} < \eta < 71 \text{ Pa-s}$ (S1 – S3), shear strain increases linearly from $0.48 < e_x^S < 2.76$, at which point a notable increase in strain variability is observed. Variability then gradually decreases as viscosities of $71 \text{ Pa-s} < \eta < 205 \text{ Pa-s}$ (S3 – S5) are tested suggesting a possible shift in flow mechanism dominance. It is also in this range of viscosities that the transition between 0° and 90° regions becomes less and less abrupt. For specimens tested at 205 Pa-s , the largest average shear strain was observed ($e_x^S = 4.27$) and the transitional resin rich zones that are visible in all previous cases have disappeared completely.

6 RECYCLING PROCESS MAP

Having identified a range of resin viscosities for which shear flow is most favoured ($142 - 205 \text{ Pa-s}$), the phenomenological models populated in Section 4 were used to produce the recycling process map shown in Figure 11. This map shows combinations of cure temperature, cycle time, and staging degree-of-cure that satisfy a resin viscosity of 200 Pa-s . 200 Pa-s was chosen as an example because this viscosity yielded the highest average shear flow observed during the flow-compaction trials. For a case in which cycle time should not exceed 5 minutes, Figure 11 shows that cure temperatures above 170°C and staging degrees-of-cure from $0.55 < \alpha_{\text{stage}} < 0.63$ would yield appropriate processing conditions.

Figure 11: Recycling process map generated for a resin processing viscosity of 200 Pa-s .

7 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, this paper has presented the reader with a recycling framework designed to make compression moulding of uncured prepreg offcuts into complex semi-structural components possible. A comprehensive thermochemical resin characterization, as well as 1-D flow-compaction trials were carried out and the results show a strong relationship between resin viscosity and shear flow. A recycling process map was presented in which flow tailoring and cycle time customization is achieved by increasing the resin's initial degree-of-cure through staging. Finally, compression moulding trials carried out on more complex geometry parts will provide further insight into the range of desirable processing viscosities. It would then be possible to adapt this framework to situations that require a balance between percolation and shear flow.

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